

Diallyldithiocarbamidohydrazone (Dalzin) as an Analytical Reagent. Part VI. Colorimetric Determination of Palladium

N. K. Dutt and K. P. Sen Sarma

Dalzin has been used as a colorimetric reagent for palladium. The reagent is free from any absorption in the region 360-700 m μ . The yellow complex has maximum absorption below 360 m μ , but all optical density measurements have been carried out at 365 m μ . Beer's law is obeyed within 1-20 ppm. of Pd. Interference by other ions has been avoided by using versenate (EDTA) as a masking agent. The molar ratio method gives the ratio of palladium to dalzin as 1:1 in the coloured complex.

The colorimetric methods for determination of palladium are developed in connection with platinum analysis, but very few of them yield reasonably accurate results with μ g. quantities. *p*-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-rhodamine¹ is used for the detection of palladium, but no application of this reagent for the quantitative determination of the metal has been reported. Overholser and Yoe² have shown that compounds containing the *p*-nitrosophenylamino group, *p*-NO.C₆H₄N, form highly coloured complexes with palladous salts and developed colorimetric methods for determinations of the metal, using *p*-nitrosodiphenylamine and *p*-nitrosodimethyl(ethyl)amine. Several other organic thio compounds like rubianic acid and its derivatives, 2-mercaptoquinoline and 2-mercaptobenzimidazole have been used by Ráy and Xavier³ for the colorimetric determination of palladium.

Dalzin forms an orange-coloured complex with palladium which could be extracted by many organic solvents, chloroform being the best.

Estimation of Palladium by Solvent Extraction

A study of the effect of diverse ions like Cu²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺, Mo⁶⁺, W⁶⁺, V⁵⁺, Ag⁺, Hg⁺, etc. was found to interfere in the estimation of palladium. Interference due to these ions can be eliminated by the use of EDTA as a masking agent and extracting the palladium-dalzin complex by chloroform.

Palladium, although it forms a complex with EDTA, reacts preferentially with dalzin in presence of EDTA. At low *pH*, EDTA is precipitated in the free state and at higher *pH*, although the complex is thrown down, it could be extracted with chloroform as the complex is highly soluble in this solvent. With pure palladium, experiments can be carried out at a low *pH* (1.5-2.4).

1. Feigl *et al.*, *Mikrochem.*, 1931, 9, 165.

2. *Labor. Chem. Són.*, 1941, 63, 3224.

3. *This Journal*, 1958, 35, 432, 589, 633, 725; Xavier, Ph.D. thesis.

In presence of versene Cu, Co, and Ni are not precipitated, nor they form coloured complexes with dalzin. The coloured versene complexes of these elements are not extractable by chloroform.

The addition of sodium versenate solution does not affect the intensity of the palladium-dalzin colour.

The orange-yellow palladium dalzinate solution and the dalzin solution show maximum absorption in the ultraviolet region below 360 $m\mu$. In the region between 360 and 700 $m\mu$, the reagent solution (either in chloroform or acetone; acetone solution was used in the expts.), however, shows no absorption, whereas the palladium dalzinate in chloroform shows quite a high optical density at 360-370 $m\mu$. All optical density measurements for the coloured complex were therefore made at 365 $m\mu$.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard palladium solution was prepared by dissolving palladous chloride (Johnson Mathey and Co.) in HCl (conc.) and diluting with distilled water. The palladium content of the solution was determined by dimethylglyoxime. Dalzin solution : 0.1% acetone solution. EDTA solution : 1% aqueous solution.

Absorption Curve.—To the palladium solution in a 50 ml separating funnel an EDTA solution (1.5 ml), followed by 1 ml of dalzin solution, was added. The mixture was shaken well with chloroform (5 ml) each time twice or thrice; the extracts were collected in a standard 50 ml flask and the volume was made to the mark with chloroform. The absorption curve of the palladium complex (Pd=8 ppm), employing dalzin solution as blank, is shown in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1, Pd—8 ppm reagent with Pd against reagent as blank.

To prevent precipitation of free EDTA the pH of the solution should be maintained above 2; the optimum range of pH lies between 3 and 6 where the colour development is instantaneous. Above pH 7, the colour gradually fades out. In the absence of versene, the process can be carried out at lower pH (1.5-2.4) where the colour develops slowly. The orange-yellow solution of palladium dalzinate has been found to be quite stable for

several hours and over the temperature range of 25-40°. The palladium complex solution is found to obey Beer's law to 20 ppm. of Pd.

FIG. 2. Composition of the complex.

Composition of the Complex.—The empirical formula of the complex in solution was determined by the molar ratio method. Employing equimolecular solutions ($2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$) of the reagent and palladium, a series of solutions having the ratio of palladium to the reagent varying from 1:0.2 to 1:2 were prepared and their optical densities measured at 365 m μ . The curve (Fig. 2) shows a sharp break at the mole ratio of 1:1, which corresponds to the ratio of the constituents in the palladium complex.